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MUSKETEER

**Machine Learning to Augment Shared Knowledge in
Federated Privacy-Preserving Scenarios (MUSKETEER)**

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**D8.1 Project website and communication
material**

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Executive Summary

This document provides a summary of the design and implementation of the MUSKETEER project website.

The document includes a description of the navigation map of the public website. The actual website is available at <http://www.musketeer.eu>

Document History

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This document presents a report of the MUSKETEER project website, directly contributing to dissemination activities of the project. The project public-facing website contributes in creating awareness about the MUSKETEER project and its objectives and ensures an effective dissemination of the project ideas, activities and outcomes.

The main goals of the website are:

- to effectively communicate the MUSKETEER projects results,
- to promote the dissemination events of the project.

Subsequent chapters of this document present a description of the structure of the website, brochure and social media accounts of the MUSKETEER project and the intended use of each page that is included in the site.

The website address is:

<http://www.musketeer.eu>

1.2 Document Structure

The document is structured in three main sections: website, brochure and social media.

2 Website

In this chapter, we first outline the main structure of the MUSKETEER website and then for each page we present and describe its basic functionality, appearance and features. Each section focuses on describing in detail the functionalities of the site and discusses the operations available to visitors of the MUSKETEER website.

Figure 1. Home

The website is structured in five different sections: About, Publications, Objectives, Consortium and Contact. Additionally, Twitter and LinkedIn buttons have been added to the header.

2.1 About

In this section a summary of the project is included. This section will increase its content as the project progresses. New subsections can be added also for each of the different work packages.

Figure 2. About

2.2 Publications

Under the main Publications section, all MUSKETEER publications will be included. This section will contain several subsections with the different types of publications: journal articles, deliverables, brochure, communication material, links to demonstrators, etc.

Figure 3. Publications

2.3 Objectives

In this section we clearly state the 5 main objectives of the project.

OBJECTIVES

MUSKETEER has 5 main objectives

OBJECTIVE 1

Machine Learning over a high variety of different privacy-preserving scenarios.

OBJECTIVE 2

Providing robustness against external and internal threats.

OBJECTIVE 3

Enhancement of the Data Economy.

OBJECTIVE 4

Providing a standardized and extensible architecture.

OBJECTIVE 5

Industrial demonstration of the technology advances in operational environment.

Figure 4. Objectives

2.4 Consortium

This Consortium section introduces the project partners. The organizations involved in the project are included, together with a short description of each partner, including links to their respective social network accounts, thus providing visitors the option to redirect to all the partners' websites.

CONSORTIUM

Partners

Figure 5. Consortium

2.5 Contact

A contact form is provided for anyone interested in getting in touch with the project.

CONTACT US
For more information, please do not hesitate to contact us

Your name (required)

Your Email (required)

Subject (required)

Your message

I consent to having this website store my submitted information so they can respond to my inquiry. *

This form collects your name and email so that we can reach you back. Check out our [Privacy Policy](#) page to fully understand how we protect and manage your submitted data.

SEND

Figure 6. Contact us

3 Brochure

A two-page brochure was produced to provide an overview of the project and can be found on the “Publications” page of the MUSKETEER website.

The Brochure includes general information about MUSKETEER project.

Figure 7. Brochure (1/2)

Figure 8. Brochure (2/2)

4 Social Media

4.1 Twitter

The Twitter handle [@H2020Musketeer](https://twitter.com/H2020Musketeer) is registered and used for promoting the project.

The www.MUSKETEER.eu site links to this Twitter account and also displays recent tweets on the first page.

Figure 9. Twitter account

4.2 LinkedIn

The LinkedIn group “H2020_MUSKETEER” currently has 22 members and is used to promote the project among the professional community.

<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8741148/>

Figure 10. LinkedIn group

5 Conclusions

The MUSKETEER project website was presented at the kick-off meeting on 29-30-31 January 2019. As a consequence, all the partners were able to evaluate its design, performance and contents in order to suggest any modifications and improvements, which were accomplished in the last months before completing this deliverable.

The website, which is available at www.MUSKETEER.eu, consists of different public pages where all the related information – description, objectives, partners, contact – is displayed. In addition, an administrative tool allows the webmaster to update and add content. Moreover, all the partners will have access to the private content management system where official documents, reports, dissemination material and other information is stored.

Additionally, Twitter and LinkedIn social networks accounts have been created for MUSKETEER project.

Finally, a project brochure is now available and will be used for dissemination and communication purposes. It included the most relevant information of the project.